

Women in Veterinary: Their Roles, Problems and Future

Urfeya Mirza

Department of veterinary surgery and radiology, FVSc & AH, SKUAST-K

*Corresponding author: urfeyamirza@gmail.com

Abstract

Veterinary profession has transformed and witnessed a considerable increase in the number of female veterinarians during the recent decades. This transformation can be attributed to the increase in the number of student places at graduate level and the general trend for young girls to outperform their male counterparts in academic grade achievement. Women veterinarians are rapidly approaching that pattern of equal, full-time professional work and have entered all specialties. However, the potential of female veterinarians is typically not fully exploited. Professional accreditation is inadequate to challenge the gender-based discrimination in terms of opportunities, pay and benefit packages. However, in future the unwarranted fears about the feminization of the profession and its presumed deleterious effects will fade into obscurity, along with the previous myths about women's unsuitability and the veterinary profession will find ways to ensure that all its graduates, regardless of gender, will achieve the rewards they deserve.

Keywords: Discrimination, Female, Gender, Opportunities, Role, Veterinary profession

Introduction

Like human medicine, the veterinary medical profession had traditionally excluded women on the basis of their gender, however, as observed by Slater and Slater (2000), veterinary medicine has quickly reversed this trend and is starting to attract '*increasing numbers of scientifically educated women, women whose training and abilities offer them a spectrum of professional options, but who chose veterinary medicine*'. But, this is a fairly recent development. Women's interest in animal health has a long history that can be traced back to the middle ages. With the emergence of professional veterinary care in the 19th century, as was true for other professions during this period, women were excluded from professional training on the basis of gender. The typical attitude toward women of the period who wished to become veterinarians was expressed in an editorial in 1897, in which was observed that "no lady would like to perform those operations

which are the almost daily work of the veterinary practitioner (unless she) is prepared to unsex herself completely (Jones, 1998).” Veterinary medical profession has moved from a tradition of exclusion on the basis of gender to one of inclusion more quickly than any of the traditional professions. World has witnessed a considerable increase in the number of female veterinarians during the recent decades. According to Lofstedt (2003), feminization of veterinary profession can be attributed to:

- elimination of gender-based admission discrimination
- improvement in chemical restraint for large animals
- increase in the number of female role models
- caring portrayal of veterinarians in literature and television

By way of contrast, Lofstedt (2003) suggests that the significant reduction in male veterinary students might also be attributed to men’s reluctance to enter careers with low or stagnant incomes, or to engage in a profession that may have lost some of its autonomy as a result of increased corporate practices. The increased number of women choosing veterinary medicine as a career might also be attributed to the general increase in the number of student places at third level, higher entry requirements and the general trend for young girls to outperform their male counterparts in academic grade achievement.

Role of Women in Modernization of Veterinary Profession

Changes in the nature and practice of veterinary medicine itself helped to appease fears about women’s participation. Although large animal and farm animal practice remained important, companion animal practice became increasingly more common. Even in equine and food animal practice, however, modern technology and the development of safer sedatives and tranquilizers made the strength of practitioners increasingly irrelevant. The confluence of these legal, social, and scientific changes served to open opportunities for academically talented women in greater numbers than ever before.

As veterinary scientific knowledge has expanded in recent decades, women have entered all specialties. Moreover, they have led the way in development of some of the newer specialties and have participated in other newly created specialties such as oncology, cardiology, dentistry, and epidemiology. Many of these newer specialties were created or expanded in recent decades, precisely those times marked by an increase in the number of women in graduate training

(Brakeman, 1997). In addition, during these decades, many more graduates of veterinary colleges have sought admissions in masters and even doctoral degree programs (Gehrke, 1997). Women veterinarians are rapidly approaching that pattern of equal, full-time professional work (Gehrke, 1996).

Problems faced by women veterinarians

While the attraction to higher status professional occupations on the part of women is understandable, professional accreditation is often insufficient to challenge embedded gender-based discrimination. Thus, the potential of female professionals is typically not fully exploited. In the case of veterinary medicine, this is evidenced by the fact that, despite women's increased participation in the profession, the majority of veterinary practitioners, particularly those who own or run their own veterinary practice, are still male, although this is expected to change in the future as a predominately female graduate population begins to enter the workforce. Consistent with mainstream gender and career literatures, there has also been some evidence of inequalities within the veterinary medicine sector in terms of job offers, pay and benefit packages (Felsted and Volk, 2000; Smith, 2006), with women often perceived as unsuitable for veterinary leadership or management positions because of concerns around maternity leave, family responsibilities or the specific masculinity ascribed to large and farm animal practice (Slater and Slater, 2000). Nevertheless, studies do generally show that women have a harder time combining family and career, and for good reason. Despite this, today and in the foreseeable future, the lines separating the public and private lives of men and women will become blurred, especially as the work force participation of women meets that of men (Glazer and Slater, 1986).

The Future of Veterinary Medicine for Women

More women, irrespective of marital and maternal status, are entering the work force full-time. Not only do women outnumber men in undergraduate colleges, but increasing numbers of them are majoring in the sciences (Glenn, 1996). This augurs well for continued growth in the number of eligible candidates for veterinary schools. Under these circumstances, the unwarranted fears about the feminization of the profession and its presumed deleterious effects will fade into obscurity, along with the previous myths about women's unsuitability. When the profession takes full cognizance of its high societal and economic value, it will begin to find ways to ensure that all its graduates, regardless of gender, will achieve the rewards they deserve.

There are also signs that the structure of veterinary health care delivery is changing in ways that may be beneficial to women and men. Recent corporate models of veterinary care suggest at least one model for the future. This kind of veterinary health care delivery system offers practitioners the advantages of a known work schedule and employee benefits without afterhours emergency duty, a work profile that combines more easily with a social and familial life. Whatever other solutions are offered in the future, the needs of women will have to be taken into consideration. Women will constitute a substantial part of the profession and will occupy places in all ranks of the power structure.

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